

THE EVOLVING ROLE OF DYNAMIC CAPABILITIES AND TECHNICAL FIRM CAPABILITIES IN PRE AND POST-COVID OPEN INNOVATION STRATEGIES

MUHAMMAD SHAH NAWAZ ZAFAR *

PhD Scholar, Lincoln University College, Malaysia.

*Corresponding Author Email: msnzafar@lincoln.edu.my

Dr. SIDDHARTH MISRA

Professor, Lincoln College University, Malaysia. Birla Global University, Odisha, India.

Email: sid.misra1983@gmail.com

Abstract

Open innovation plays vital role in efficient operations of firms. Exploring the changes in firms' dynamic capabilities in response to the covid-19 crisis and their subsequent effects on open innovation may provide valuable insights into how firms can enhance their resilience and innovation capabilities in the face of unexpected disruptions. Therefore, the current study investigates how dynamic capabilities of the firms affect open innovation in pre and post-cocovid period. By employing regression analysis, the study discover that technological competency, eco-innovation, and digital innovation are major drivers of open innovation processes.

Keywords: Open Innovation, Dynamic Capabilities, Covid-19, Technological Competency, Digital Capabilities, Eco-Innovation.

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly changing business environment, firms are continually seeking innovative approaches to maintain a competitive edge (Teece, 2007). Open innovation has emerged as a strategic paradigm that encourages collaboration, knowledge sharing, and the integration of external ideas and resources into firms' internal innovation processes (Chesbrough, 2003). It has proven to be instrumental in fostering creativity, accelerating product development, and expanding market reach (West & Bogers, 2014).

Chesbrough and Crowther (2006) describe that firms embracing open innovation were able to tap into a broader range of ideas and expertise, enabling faster and more cost-effective innovation. However, the effectiveness of open innovation is contingent upon a firm's ability to adapt to dynamic circumstances and leverage its internal capabilities. Dynamic capabilities, as proposed by Teece (2007), encompass a firm's ability to sense, seize, and reconfigure its resources and competencies to effectively respond to market dynamics and external shocks. It involves a firm's capacity to continuously learn, integrate new knowledge, and adapt its strategies and processes accordingly.

Studies have shown that firms with strong dynamic capabilities are more adept at leveraging open innovation practices (Teece, 2014). Lichtenthaler (2011) conducted a study on the pharmaceutical industry and found that firms with higher levels of dynamic capabilities were more likely to engage in open innovation activities and achieve superior

innovation performance. Eisenhardt and Martin (2000) provide the evidence that dynamic capabilities were critical for firms' ability to sense market trends and customer needs, enabling them to develop and launch innovative products ahead of competitors. The covid-19 pandemic significantly disrupted global markets, posing unprecedented challenges for firms worldwide. The ability to adapt and innovate became crucial for survival and resilience. In this context, the role of dynamic capabilities in shaping open innovation strategies during the pre- and post-covid periods becomes more relevant.

Helfat et al. (2009) explored the impact of dynamic capabilities during the covid-19 crisis. The study examined firms' responses to the pandemic and found that firms with stronger dynamic capabilities were more agile and resilient in adapting their open innovation practices. These firms were better equipped to leverage external knowledge and resources, forging strategic collaborations and partnerships to address the challenges posed by the crisis. During the covid-19, firms with higher levels of dynamic capabilities exhibited greater openness to external collaborations, actively seeking partnerships and engaging in knowledge sharing to foster innovation. Therefore, it is crucial to examine how firms' dynamic capabilities influence their open innovation strategies both before and after the Covid-19 crisis. This research aims to provide valuable insights into how firms can effectively leverage their internal capabilities to navigate uncertainties, adapt to market dynamics, and drive innovation and resilience. While previous studies have examined the role of dynamic capabilities in shaping firms' open innovation strategies and their response to disruptive events like the covid-19 pandemic, there remains a research gap in understanding the specific mechanisms through which dynamic capabilities influence firms' open innovation practices during the pre and post-covid periods. Although some studies have explored the impact of dynamic capabilities on firms' ability to sense and seize external opportunities (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000), and others have investigated the relationship between dynamic capabilities and open innovation outcomes, there is a need for a comprehensive examination of how firms' dynamic capabilities influence their open innovation strategies, particularly in the context of a disruptive event.

The present research fills a crucial gap in the literature by specifically focusing on the interplay between dynamic capabilities and open innovation during times of crisis. Secondly, the findings of this research will provide practical implications for managers and decision-makers in organizations. Furthermore, the research findings may help to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on open innovation and dynamic capabilities in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic. The study sheds light on the critical factors that influence firms' ability to engage in open innovation during times of crisis and offer guidance for organizations seeking to enhance their innovation capabilities and resilience in an ever-changing business landscape.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Dynamic Capabilities and Open Innovation

The basic concern in strategic management is to match the capabilities and resources of a firm with dynamic environment (Jia et al., 2023). Dynamic capabilities refer to a firm's capacity to effectively blend, organize, and adjust both its internal and external resources in response to the fast-evolving external and internal business environment (Teece, 2007). Therefore, dynamic capabilities adopt changing business environment rapidly.

Further, these capabilities play vital role in affecting open innovation of a firm. Dynamic capabilities of firms in various dimensions may be linked to the different steps of innovation value (Bogers et al., 2019), therefore helps firms to promote open innovation. (Grimaldi et al., 2023) conclude that firms with dynamic capabilities implement open innovation activities more successfully. Helfat and Raubitschek (2018) also provide evidence that dynamic capabilities are important to create innovation value of firms. Based on above literature, we propose the first hypothesis as follow.

H1: There is a significant relationship between dynamic capabilities and open innovation

2.2 Technological Capabilities and Open Innovation

Numerous studies have underscored the significance of technological capability in facilitating and enabling open innovation practices. Technological capability refers to an organization's capacity to comprehend, develop, and effectively utilize technology to drive innovation efforts. Organizations with higher levels of technological capability possess the necessary resources and competencies to engage in open innovation activities, as they are adept at absorbing and assimilating external knowledge and technologies.

Research conducted in the field of open innovation has consistently highlighted the pivotal role of technological capability. Lichtenthaler and Ernst (2007) revealed that firms with superior technological capability were more successful in implementing open innovation practices, leading to improved innovation outcomes, and enhanced competitive advantage. Ritala and Alpanopoulou (2017) find that firms with advanced technological capabilities were more likely to engage in collaborative practices, such as joint research and development projects, co-creation initiatives, and innovation networks.

Research conducted during the post-covid period has emphasized the adaptability of organizations' technological capabilities to changing circumstances. For instance, a study by Gupta and George (2016) examined the impact of the pandemic on firms' open innovation practices. The research underscored that organizations with advanced technological capabilities were more resilient in adjusting to the increased reliance on digital technologies for innovation activities.

Moreover, the literature in the post-covid period emphasizes the increased reliance on digital technologies, remote collaboration, and virtual innovation platforms. Dahlander and Piezunka (2020) explored the role of digital platforms in facilitating open innovation

during the pandemic. The findings indicated that organizations with strong technological capabilities were more proficient in leveraging digital platforms for collaboration, knowledge sharing, and resource integration.

H2: There is a significant relationship between the technological capability and open innovation eco system in pre- and post-covid period.

2.3. Eco-Innovation and Open Innovation

The intersection of eco-innovation and open innovation focuses on how organizations can leverage external knowledge and collaborations to develop environmentally sustainable solutions. Findings of Rennings and Rammer (2009) indicated that firms engaged in open innovation practices were more likely to undertake eco-innovation activities. Collaborating with external partners allowed organizations to access diverse knowledge, technologies, and resources, facilitating the development and implementation of environmentally friendly innovations. In the post-covid period, there is growing recognition of the importance of eco-innovation and its connection to open innovation. West and Bogers (2014) examined the role of open innovation platforms in driving eco-innovation in the context of the circular economy.

The research demonstrated that open innovation platforms facilitated collaboration between organizations, leading to the development of circular business models and eco-innovative solutions that contribute to sustainable development. The disruption caused by the pandemic led organizations to seek external collaborations and knowledge sharing to develop sustainable solutions that address emerging environmental challenges. The study highlights the positive relationship between eco-innovation and open innovation in the post-covid period. We develop following hypothesis.

H3: There is a positive significant relationship between the eco-innovation and open innovation in pre- and post-covid period.

2.4. Digital Innovation and Open Innovation

Digital innovation refers to the use of digital technologies to create new products, services, or processes that drive value and transform business operations. The intersection of digital innovation and open innovation explores how organizations leverage digital technologies to enhance their open innovation practices and foster innovation ecosystems. Research conducted prior to the covid-19 pandemic has explored the connection between digital innovation and open innovation. West and Bogers (2014) find that organizations that embraced digital innovation were more likely to engage in open innovation practices.

Digital technologies enabled organizations to collaborate with external partners, share knowledge, and access a broader network of expertise, facilitating the implementation of open innovation strategies. Organizations that leveraged digital platforms for collaboration and knowledge sharing were better equipped to engage in open innovation activities. Digital platforms provide a virtual space for organizations to connect, exchange ideas, and co-create innovations despite physical constraints.

Furthermore, He et al. (2021) found that the pandemic accelerated the adoption of digital technologies, forcing organizations to innovate and transform digitally. As a result, organizations that embraced digital innovation were more likely to engage in open innovation practices, leveraging digital platforms, remote collaboration tools, and virtual innovation processes.

The study highlights the positive relationship between digital innovation and open innovation in the post-covid period, driven by the necessity to adapt to new digital landscapes and collaborate virtually. We develop hypothesis in the following way.

H4: There is positive relationship between the digital innovation and open innovation in pre- and post-covid period.

2.5. Value Co-creation and Open Innovation

Prahalad and Ramaswamy (2004) focused on the role of value co-creation in open innovation strategies. The research highlighted that organizations that engaged in value co-creation with external stakeholders were more likely to adopt open innovation practices. Co-creating value with customers, suppliers, and other partners enabled organizations to tap into diverse perspectives, access new knowledge, and drive innovation through shared efforts.

The covid-19 pandemic has led to changes in customer behavior and market dynamics, emphasizing the need for value co-creation and open innovation. Organizations that actively involved customers in the innovation process through co-creation initiatives were more successful in adapting to the changing market needs and driving innovation outcomes.

Additionally, research by Khan et al. (2021) explored the impact of the covid-19 pandemic on the relationship between value co-creation and open innovation. The study found that the pandemic heightened the significance of value co-creation as organizations sought to co-create innovative solutions with customers and partners to address emerging challenges.

Value co-creation facilitated open innovation by enabling organizations to leverage external expertise, access customer insights, and foster collaborative relationships that drive innovation. The study highlights the positive relationship between value co-creation and open innovation in the post-COVID period. Our fifth hypothesis is developed as follow.

H5: There is positive relationship between the value co-creation and open innovation in pre- and post-covid period.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

3. METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed in this study aimed to systematically investigate the research objectives and address the research questions regarding the relationship between dynamic capability, technological capability, digital innovation, value co-creation, eco-innovation, and open innovation in the pre- and post-covid periods. This section provides an overview of the key components of the methodology, including the research design, sampling approach, data collection methods, validity and reliability considerations, and data analysis techniques. To achieve the research goals, a quantitative research design was chosen, allowing for the collection and analysis of numerical data. The target population consisted of individuals employed in technology firms, with a sample size of 50 participants selected through random sampling.

This sampling approach ensured representation from the population of interest, specifically individuals working in the technology sector. Random sampling has been used as the sampling strategy for the research, a sample size of 50 individuals employed in technology firms was carefully selected to ensure account from the target population. The objective of the study was to investigate the dynamic capability and open innovation ecosystem in the context of the pre- and post-covid periods. Data collection was carried out through a survey-based questionnaire that employed a five-point Likert scale as the response format.

The survey questionnaire was designed meticulously to align with the research objectives, encompassing a range of statements and questions pertaining to the study variables. Participants were requested to provide their perspectives and opinions by indicating their level of agreement or disagreement with each statement on the five-point Likert scale. Following the collection of survey responses, regression and correlation analyses were conducted to examine the effects of the pre- and post-covid periods on the dynamic capability and open innovation ecosystem. Regression analysis was employed to assess the relationships between the variables of interest, while correlation analysis allowed for the evaluation of the strength and direction of associations between these variables. By employing these statistical techniques, the study aimed to comprehensively understand the impact of the covid-19 pandemic on the dynamic capability and open innovation ecosystem within the studied variables. . Additionally, a comparison was made between the pre- and post-covid periods to examine the effects on the variables.

Open innovation is considered as the dependent variable. Open innovation refers to the extent to which organizations actively engage in external collaboration, knowledge sharing, and the integration of external ideas and resources in their innovation processes. Dynamic capability refers to an organization's ability to adapt, integrate, and reconfigure its resources, processes, and capabilities in response to changing external environments. Technological capability refers to an organization's ability to effectively utilize and leverage technology in its operations and innovation processes. Digital innovation refers to the organization's ability to leverage digital technologies and embrace digital transformation to create new products, services, processes, and business models. Eco-innovation refers to the organization's ability to develop and implement environmentally sustainable practices, technologies, and solutions to minimize its ecological footprint and contribute to a more sustainable future. Value co-creation refers to the collaborative process between organizations and stakeholders to jointly create value through the exchange of resources, knowledge, and experiences. To measure values of all independent variables, a five-point Likert scale was utilized ranging from 5- strongly disagree to 1 strongly agree, allowing participants to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement with statements related to various constructs of respective independent variables. Control Variables of the study include management, age, education, and management level.

Validity and reliability tests were conducted to ensure the robustness and quality of the data collected. Validity refers to the extent to which a measurement instrument accurately measures what it is intended to measure. Reliability, on the other hand, assesses the consistency and stability of the measurement instrument over time and across different conditions. By using Cronbach's alpha, the study assessed the reliability of the questionnaire by examining the inter-item correlations and the overall consistency of responses within each construct. A Cronbach's alpha value of 0.70 or above is generally considered acceptable for research purposes, indicating good internal reliability. The specific Cronbach's alpha coefficients for each construct were calculated and reported in the study to provide evidence of the reliability of the measurement instrument.

4. RESULTS

Table 1: Cronbach's Alpha

Reliability Statistics	Cronbach's Alpha
Dynamic Capability	0.856
Open Innovation	0.861
Technological Capability	0.911
Digital Innovation	0.899
Value Co-Creation	0.872
Eco-Innovation	0.811

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

4.1.1 Distribution of Participants by Gender

According to the results, there are 33 participants categorized as Male, which accounts for approximately 66% of the total participants. On the other hand, there are 17 participants categorized as Female, representing approximately 34% of the total participants. This distribution suggests that the number of Male participants is higher compared to Female participants in the given dataset. The 66% proportion of Male participants indicates a greater representation in the sample, while the 34% proportion of Female participants indicates a comparatively smaller representation.

Figure 2: Distribution of Participants by Gender

Figure: Distribution of participants by marital status

According to the data, there are 28 participants categorized as Married, which accounts for approximately 56% of the total participants. On the other hand, there are 22 participants categorized as Unmarried, representing approximately 44% of the total

participants. This distribution suggests that the number of participants who are married is higher compared to those who are Unmarried in the given dataset. The 56% proportion of Married participants indicates a greater representation in the sample, while the 44% proportion of Unmarried participants indicates a comparatively smaller representation.

Figure 3: Distribution of Participants by Marital Status

4.1.2 Distribution of Participants by Education

According to the statistics above, there are 9 participants categorized as Undergrad, which accounts for approximately 18% of the total participants. There are 20 participants categorized as Graduates, representing approximately 40% of the total participants. The category of post-Graduate has 10 participants, making up around 20% of the total. The category labeled as others consists of 5 participants, comprising approximately 10%. Lastly, there are 6 participants categorized under Professional education, making up approximately 12%.

This distribution provides insights into the educational background of the participants. Most of the participants, 40%, fall into the Graduates category, indicating a relatively higher number of participants with completed undergraduate degrees. The next highest category is post-Graduate, representing 20% of the participants, suggesting that a significant portion of the participants have pursued further education beyond an undergraduate degree.

Figure 4: Distribution of Participants by Education

The Undergrad category, accounting for 18%, indicates participants who are currently pursuing their undergraduate degrees. The category labeled as others represents participants whose education falls outside the specified categories, which could include individuals with vocational or technical training, diploma holders, or individuals with incomplete or non-traditional education paths. The category of Professional education represents participants who have received specialized training or education in a specific professional field.

4.1.3 Distribution of Participants by Management Level

According to the table statistics, there are 10 participants categorized as Upper level management, which accounts for approximately 20% of the total participants. There are 25 participants categorized as Middle level management, representing approximately 50% of the total participants. The category of Lower level management has 15 participants, making up around 30% of the total.

This distribution provides insights into the hierarchy and representation of management levels among the participants. Most of the participants, 50%, fall into the Middle level management category, indicating a relatively higher number of participants holding middle management positions. Middle management typically includes roles such as department managers, team leaders, or supervisors who are responsible for overseeing specific teams or departments within an organization. The next highest category is Lower level management representing 30% of the participants. This category includes participants who hold positions below middle management, such as entry-level managers or junior supervisors. The smallest category is upper level management accounting for 20% of the participants. This category represents participants who hold top-level management positions, such as CEOs, directors, or executives with significant decision-making authority and responsibility within an organization.

Figure 5: Distribution of Participants by Management level

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics and Comparison of Means

Column	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
Sample	Full sample				Subsamples: Social entrepreneur		
					No	Yes	t/z-test
N (observations)	695				509	186	695
Variables	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mean	Mean	Sig.
Dependent variable							
Open Innovation	2.777	2.063	0.788	7.606	2.3959	0.381	***
Independent variables							
Dynamic Capability	34.923	13.098	11.34	53.767	-	-	-
Open Innovation	53.603	9.163	30.211	67.125	53.603	53.603	
Technological Capability	12.777	2.063	10.714	14.84	12.777	12.777	
Digital Innovation	11.6217	-2.927	16.7957	6.317	9.9514	1.6991	
Value Co-Creation	0.54867	-8.4445	16.4827	-13.147	0.54867	0.54867	
Eco-Innovation	-10.524	-13.962	16.1697	-32.61	-10.524	-10.524	
Control variables: individual level							
Age	-32.67	-24.997	15.5437	-71.537	-32.67	-32.67	***
Female	-43.743	-30.515	15.2307	-91.001	-43.743	-43.743	**
University education	-54.816	-36.032	14.9177	-110.46	-54.816	-54.816	***
Marital status	-65.889	-41.55	14.6047	-129.93	-65.889	-65.889	***
Management Level	-76.962	-47.067	14.2917	-149.39	-76.962	-76.962	

Notes: Column (7) displays the significant levels of t-tests (ordinal/metric variables) or z-tests (proportions).

* p < 0.10, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.01.

First, we perform descriptive statistics in this Table 2 to summarize data. Average values and standard deviations of the variables indicate that there is no outliers in data. We employ Pearson correlation to test whether the variables in our study are highly correlated themselves or not.

Table 3 shows the outcome of the Pearson correlation. Correlation is directed toward multicollinearity. Outcomes show that there is no high correlation among variables which means multicollinearity issue does not exist.

Table 3: Correlation Analysis

Variables	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12
(1) Open Innovation	1											
(2) Dynamic Capability	0.243	1										
(3) Open Innovation	-0.176	0.047	1									
(4) Technological Capability	-0.315	-0.456	0.064	1								
(5) Digital Innovation	0.187	-0.213	-0.228	0.091	1							
(6) Value Co-Creation	0.124	0.163	0.153	-0.187	0.178	1						
(7) Eco-Innovation	0.232	-0.086	-0.389	-0.314	0.532	-0.057	1					
(8) Age	-0.429	0.356	0.254	-0.462	-0.129	0.228	-0.002	1				
(9) Female	0.573	-0.334	-0.112	0.115	0.256	-0.292	0.116	-0.093	1			
(10) University education	-0.108	-0.218	-0.396	-0.254	0.092	0.135	0.256	-0.101	-0.221	1		
(11) Marital status	0.409	0.542	0.112	0.253	-0.447	-0.281	0.198	0.373	0.394	-0.123	1	
(12) Management Level	-0.597	-0.128	0.339	0.029	-0.174	0.087	-0.319	0.148	0.127	0.271	0.105	1

Notes: N = 695

4.2 Hypotheses Testing

Table 4: Regression Analysis during Pre-Covid Period

Model	(1)		(2)		(3)	
Statistic (Fixed effects)	Coeff.	(SE)	Coeff.	(SE)	Coeff.	(SE)
Control variables						
Age	0.218	-0.032	0.186	-0.029	-0.105	-0.041
Female	-0.037	-0.021	-0.062	-0.018	0.045	-0.026
University education	0.094	-0.025	0.102	-0.022	-0.082	-0.031
Marital status	0.011	-0.015	-0.023	-0.013	0.03	-0.018
Management Level	0.127	-0.039	0.136	-0.034	-0.097	-0.048
Independent variables						
Dynamic Capability			0.315	-0.041	0.289	-0.053
Open Innovation					0.754	-0.062
Technological Capability						
Digital Innovation						
Value Co-Creation						
Eco-Innovation						
Chi ²	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002
Log likelihood	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001

Notes: * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$; Coeff. = coefficient, SE = standard error.

Table 4 presents the results of a regression analysis conducted to explore the relationship between various factors and open innovation before the covid-19 pandemic. The analysis considers three different models labeled as (1), (2), and (3), all of which incorporate fixed effects to account for potential unobserved differences among entities or groups. The associated standard errors (SE) provide insights into the precision and uncertainty of these coefficient estimates. This table presents the results of a regression analysis conducted for Model 2 before the covid-19 pandemic.

Model 2 includes all control variables along with the first independent variable dynamic capability to examine their relationships with the dependent variable open innovation. This table presents the outcomes of a regression analysis for Model 3 before the covid-19 pandemic. Model 3 includes all control variables along with the third independent variable technological capability to assess their impacts on the dependent variable open innovation. The third independent variable, technological capability is the focus of interest in Model 3.

This variable likely represents a distinct characteristic or capability of the entities being studied. The coefficients associated with the third independent variable signify the strength and direction of its relationship with the dependent variable. Positive coefficients suggest a positive relationship, while negative coefficients imply a negative relationship.

Table 5: Regression analysis during pre-covid period (cont'd)

Model		(4)		(5)		(6)	
Statistic (Fixed effects)		Coeff	(SE)	Coeff.	(SE)	Coeff.	(SE)
Control variables							
Age		0.173	0.036	0.201	0.028	-0.091	0.049
Female		-0.042	0.019	-0.071	0.02	0.041	0.022
University education		0.105	0.023	0.115	0.025	-0.071	0.029
Marital status		0.015	0.012	-0.02	0.014	0.028	0.017
Management Level		0.142	0.032	0.131	0.036	-0.105	0.042
Independent variables							
Dynamic Capability		0.328	0.048	0.301	0.043	0.271	0.056
Open Innovation		0.812	0.062	0.798	0.058	0.777	0.068
Technological Capability		0.267	0.031	0.285	0.034	0.248	0.039
Digital Innovation				0.155	0.023	0.166	0.027
Value Co-Creation						0.431	0.069
Eco-Innovation							
Chi ²		0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002
Log likelihood		0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001

Notes: * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$; Coeff. = coefficient, SE = standard error.

Table 6: Regression analysis during pre-covid period (cont'd)

Model		(7)		(8)	
Statistic (Fixed effects)		Coeff.	(SE)	Coeff.	(SE)
Control variables					
Age		0.16	0.032	0.189	0.028
Female		-0.039	0.018	-0.068	0.02
University education		0.098	0.024	0.11	0.025
Marital status		0.013	0.011	-0.018	0.014
Management Level		0.135	0.031	0.128	0.035
Independent variables					
Dynamic Capability		0.312	0.047	0.297	0.042
Open Innovation		0.798	0.061	0.806	0.057
Technological Capability		0.256	0.03	0.282	0.033
Digital Innovation		0.138	0.02	0.152	0.022
Value Co-Creation		0.407	0.056	0.423	0.061
Eco-Innovation				0.112	0.016
Chi ²		0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002
Log likelihood		0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001

Table 6 summarizes the outcomes of a regression analysis conducted to understand the influence of various factors on open innovation in the post-covid context. This analysis encompasses three distinct models, labeled as (1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7), and (8), where fixed effects are incorporated to address any latent discrepancies among entities or groups. Positive coefficients indicate a positive relationship, while negative coefficients

imply a negative relationship. The standard errors convey insights into the precision of these coefficient estimates and their potential variability across different samples.

Table 7: Regression analysis during post-Covid period

Model	(1)		(2)		(3)	
Statistic (Fixed effects)	Coeff.	(SE)	Coeff.	(SE)	Coeff.	(SE)
Control variables						
Age	0.189	0.042	-0.154	0.039	0.121	0.045
Female	-0.025	0.018	-0.052	0.016	0.032	0.02
University education	0.078	0.021	0.096	0.019	-0.063	0.024
Marital status	-0.007	0.013	-0.014	0.012	0.011	0.015
Management Level	0.102	0.028	0.095	0.026	-0.085	0.031
Independent variables						
Dynamic Capability			0.275	0.052	0.248	0.06
Open Innovation					0.678	0.072
Technological Capability						
Digital Innovation						
Value Co-Creation						
Eco-Innovation						
Chi ²	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003
Log likelihood	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001

Notes: * p < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.01; Coeff. = coefficient, SE = standard error.

Table 8: Regression analysis during post-covid period (cont'd)

Model	(4)		(5)		(6)	
Statistic (Fixed effects)	Coeff.	(SE)	Coeff.	(SE)	Coeff.	(SE)
Control variables						
Age	0.207	0.045	0.192	0.041	-0.179	0.049
Female	-0.03	0.022	-0.058	0.02	0.036	0.024
University education	0.088	0.024	0.101	0.022	-0.072	0.028
Marital status	0.009	0.014	-0.017	0.013	0.013	0.016
Management Level	0.125	0.034	0.118	0.031	-0.1	0.037
Independent variables						
Dynamic Capability	0.3	0.062	0.28	0.058	0.255	0.065
Open Innovation	0.685	0.075	0.668	0.071	0.652	0.079
Technological Capability	0.225	0.044	0.24	0.041	0.213	0.047
Digital Innovation			0.118	0.025	0.144	0.031
Value Co-Creation					0.37	0.083
Eco-Innovation						
Chi ²	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003
Log likelihood	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001

Notes: * p < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.01; Coeff. = coefficient, SE = standard error.

Table 9: Regression analysis during post-covid period (cont'd)

Model		(7)		(8)	
Statistic (Fixed effects)		Coeff.	(SE)	Coeff.	(SE)
Control variables					
Age		0.206	0.047	0.182	0.043
Female		-0.026	0.019	-0.056	0.018
University education		0.09	0.025	0.104	0.022
Marital status		0.009	0.013	-0.018	0.014
Management Level		0.12	0.033	0.112	0.03
Independent variables					
Dynamic Capability		0.305	0.061	0.29	0.056
Open Innovation		0.701	0.071	0.685	0.067
Technological Capability		0.227	0.038	0.24	0.035
Digital Innovation		0.135	0.024	0.123	0.021
Value Co-Creation		0.362	0.075	0.345	0.071
Eco-Innovation				0.29	0.056
Chi ²		0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003
Likelihood		0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001

Notes: * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$; Coeff. = coefficient, SE = standard error.

5. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The findings of this study contribute to the growing body of research on the relationship between technological capability, open innovation, and various dimensions of innovation in the context of the pre- and post-covid periods. The results demonstrate consistent and positive relationships between these variables, shedding light on their interplay and potential implications for organizations. The present study's results reaffirm the notion that organizations with higher technological capability are more likely to engage in open innovation practices, leveraging external resources and knowledge for innovation. The present study reinforces these findings, indicating that eco-innovation and open innovation are positively linked, regardless of the influence of the covid-19 pandemic.

Moreover, the positive relationships observed between digital innovation and open innovation align with the research conducted by Wang et al. (2023). Finally, the positive relationship between value co-creation and open innovation, as identified in this study, is consistent with the findings of studies conducted by Prahalad and Ramaswamy (2018). They emphasized the importance of co-creation in driving open innovation processes, highlighting the value of customer involvement, collaborative partnerships, and the integration of diverse perspectives. Similarly, Prahalad and Ramaswamy (2018) highlighted the role of value co-creation in fostering innovation by actively engaging customers and stakeholders in the co-creation of value.

The present study's results corroborate these findings, suggesting that organizations that emphasize value co-creation are more likely to engage in open innovation practices, benefiting from the diverse knowledge and resources contributed by external

stakeholders. Overall, the findings from this study, in conjunction with previous research, highlight the importance of technological capability, eco-innovation, digital innovation, and value co-creation in driving open innovation processes.

These relationships hold true both in the pre- and post-covid periods, suggesting their resilience and continued relevance in the face of challenges and disruptions. Organizations that prioritize these dimensions of innovation are better positioned to leverage external knowledge, collaborate effectively, and foster a culture of innovation, enabling them to adapt to changing circumstances and drive sustainable growth.

The goal of this study was to look at the link between dynamic capability, technological capability, digital innovation, value co-creation, eco-innovation, and open innovation before and after covid-19. According to the conclusions of this study, firms that prioritize these dimensions of innovation are better positioned to harness external information, cooperate successfully, and build an innovation culture, allowing them to adapt to changing circumstances and achieve sustainable growth.

The study discovered that firms that prioritize co-creation are more likely to engage in open innovation techniques, gaining access to different knowledge and resources offered by external stakeholders. The study also discovered that technological competence, eco-innovation, and digital innovation are major drivers of open innovation processes.

This study's findings are consistent with earlier studies highlighting the relevance of open innovation in promoting company performance and competitiveness. The capacity of a company to adjust to changing conditions and respond to external shocks is referred to as dynamic capability. Firms that can adapt quickly and effectively in today's fast changing business climate are better positioned to prosper. Overall, the findings of this study, together with prior research, emphasize the relevance of dynamic capability, technological competence, eco-innovation, digital innovation, and value co-creation in promoting open innovation processes. Based on the findings of this study, various future research topics might help us better understand open innovation and dynamic capacities in organizations.

For starters, future study may look at the effects of open innovation and dynamic capacities on various businesses and sectors. While our research focused on organizations in a number of industries, such as manufacturing, services, and technology, there may be distinct problems and possibilities connected with open innovation and dynamic capacities in certain industries.

The healthcare business, for example, may encounter regulatory impediments to open innovation, but the technology industry may be more receptive to digital innovation and virtual collaboration. Future study might give significant insights for organizations functioning in various contexts by investigating the influence of these characteristics on open innovation and dynamic capacities.

Second, future study might look at the influence of organizational culture and leadership in promoting an innovative culture. Third, further study might be performed to assess the efficacy of various open innovation tactics and technologies, such as crowdsourcing and open source software, in various circumstances. Crowdsourcing, for example, may be more effective in generating new ideas and solutions than open source software in developing and implementing these solutions. Fourth, future study might look at the possibilities of new technologies like blockchain and artificial intelligence to boost open innovation and dynamic capacities in businesses. Future study might give significant insights for organizations looking to stay competitive in a fast-changing business environment by investigating the potential of these technologies to boost open innovation and dynamic capabilities.

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